

**IMPACTS OF SOCIAL STIGMAS AND STRUCTURAL BARRIERS ON
THE LIVES OF INDIVIDUALS WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM
DISORDER (ASD) AND THEIR FAMILIES: EMPHASIS ON THEIR
INCLUSION IN THE WORKPLACE**

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the redefinition of social vulnerabilities and the inclusion in the labor market of families of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). The neoperspectivist paradigm The giftedean model was used as an epistemological axis, seeking a holistic understanding of family experiences. Through the hypothetical-deductive method and a Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review, the findings revealed the influence of stigmas on family well-being and the importance of inclusive policies. However, gaps were identified, such as the lack of research adapted to diverse cultural and socioeconomic contexts. The contributions include insights for more effective public policies and inclusive business practices.

Keywords: Social Stigma. Social Inclusion. Coping Strategies. Employment Policies. Quality of Life.

RESUMO

Esta pesquisa explora a ressignificação das vulnerabilidades sociais e a inclusão no mercado de trabalho de famílias de indivíduos com Transtorno do Espectro Autista (TEA). O paradigma neoperspectivista giftedeano foi utilizado como eixo epistemológico, buscando uma compreensão holística das experiências familiares. Através do método hipotético-dedutivo e de uma Revisão Bibliográfica e Documental Narrativa, os achados revelaram a influência dos estigmas no bem-estar familiar e a importância de políticas inclusivas. Contudo, foram identificadas lacunas, como a falta de pesquisas adaptadas a contextos culturais e socioeconômicos diversos. As contribuições incluem insights para políticas públicas mais eficazes e práticas empresariais inclusivas.

Palavras-chave: Estigma Social. Inclusão Social. Estratégias de Enfrentamento. Políticas de Emprego. Qualidade de Vida.

RESUMEN

Esta investigación explora el replanteamiento de las vulnerabilidades sociales y la inclusión en el mercado laboral de familias de personas con Trastorno del Espectro Autista (TEA). Se utilizó como eje epistemológico el paradigma neoperspectivista giftediano, buscando una comprensión holística de las experiencias familiares. A través del método hipotético-deductivo y una Revisión Bibliográfica y Documental Narrativa, los hallazgos revelaron la influencia de los estigmas en el bienestar familiar y la importancia de las políticas inclusivas. Sin embargo, se identificaron lagunas, como la falta de investigaciones adaptadas a diferentes contextos culturales y socioeconómicos. Las contribuciones incluyen ideas para políticas públicas más efectivas y prácticas comerciales inclusivas.

Palabras-clave: Estigma social. Inclusión social. Estrategias de Afrontamiento. Políticas de Empleo. Calidad de vida.

1. INTRODUCTION

The issue of including individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in the job market and redefining the social vulnerabilities faced by their families has gained prominence in the scientific literature. Autism, a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by challenges in social communication and repetitive behaviors (American Psychiatric Association , 2013), affects not only diagnosed individuals but also their families, who often face stigma and social barriers (Lai et al., 2020). The present study aims to explore how these families deal with such challenges and identify strategies that promote the labor inclusion of individuals with ASD.

The social and labor inclusion of people with autism is essential for the promotion of an equitable and fair society. Studies show that participation in the labor market not only improves the quality of life of individuals with ASD, but also contributes to the reduction of social stigma (Hedley et al., 2017; Scott et al., 2019). Furthermore, social support and adaptation of families' social vulnerabilities are crucial to building a more inclusive and understanding environment (Crane et al., 2019). This study is justified by the need to better understand these dynamics and propose practical solutions.

The central problem of this research lies in the multiple difficulties faced by individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and their families, particularly with regard to social stigma and inclusion in the job market. Autism is a condition that not only affects the lives of diagnosed individuals, but also has a profound impact on their families, who often face social, economic and emotional barriers. Stigmatization and lack of understanding about ASD exacerbate these difficulties, contributing to social exclusion and limiting opportunities for development and full participation in society (Hedley et al., 2017; Scott et al., 2019; Crane et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the integration of individuals with ASD into the labor market remains a significant challenge. Many companies lack inclusive policies and practices, and the lack of adaptation of the work environment and specific training for employers perpetuates the marginalization of these individuals. Therefore, there is an urgent need to explore and better understand these dynamics in order to develop effective strategies that promote inclusion and reframe the social vulnerabilities faced by these families (Lai et al., 2020; Crane et al., 2019).

The main guiding question of this research is: How do social stigmas and structural barriers impact the lives of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and their families, especially in the context of labor inclusion? Based on this central question, specific questions were raised to guide the investigation: a) What are the main stigmas faced by individuals with autism and their families?; b) How do families of individuals with autism resignify their social vulnerabilities?; c) What is the psychological impact of stigma on families of individuals with autism?; d) What are the main barriers to the insertion of individuals with autism in the labor market?; e) What are the effective strategies to promote the labor inclusion of individuals with autism? These questions structure the analysis and discussion of the results, allowing a deeper understanding of the challenges faced and providing support for the construction of a more inclusive and equitable society.

Seeking to satisfactorily answer the problematic questions raised, this research conducts a Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review (NBDR), with the objective of analyzing how families of individuals with autism reframe their social vulnerabilities and identifying effective strategies for the insertion of these individuals in the labor market. To achieve this main objective, the following specific objectives were outlined: a) to identify the main stigmas faced by individuals with autism and their families; b) to examine the coping strategies adopted by families to deal with these vulnerabilities; c) to evaluate public policies and community initiatives aimed at the labor inclusion of people with ASD; d) to propose recommendations for companies and institutions aiming at improving the inclusion of individuals with autism in the labor market.

This work was structured in four chapters. In this Introduction, the following were presented: the theme; the justification and relevance; the problem; the problem questions; a methodological summary; the objectives; and the structure of the work. The second chapter presented the methodological basis of the research, categorizing it into: epistemological axis/pillar, logical axis/pillar, and technical axis/pillar. The third chapter presents the results and discussion; the fourth chapter presents the conclusions and final considerations; and then the references consulted.

2. METHODOLOGICAL BASIS

The methodological basis of this research is structured based on three main pillars: epistemological, logical and technical. The epistemological axis is supported by the neoperspectivist paradigm giftedean paradigm , which offers a holistic theoretical lens for understanding the complex social dynamics involving individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and their families. This paradigm, outlined by Breviário (2021, 2022, 2023), advocates the coexistence of an absolute, albeit unattainable, truth and a subjective truth, constructed from everyday experiences. By emphasizing the multiplicity of perspectives and the appreciation of human singularities, the paradigm allows research to explore the voices and experiences of families of individuals with ASD, often marginalized in traditional analyses.

In this sense, the critical and reflective approach promoted by neoperspectivism giftedean encourages the analysis of social structures and power mechanisms that perpetuate the social and labor exclusion of these families. This epistemological perspective is essential for formulating the research hypotheses, since it seeks both to understand how families resignify their vulnerabilities in the face of stigma and to identify the transformative role that public policies and inclusive business practices can play in promoting social inclusion. The choice of this paradigm underpins the data analysis and discussions, allowing for an effective theoretical triangulation between critical approaches from the social sciences and empirical and documentary analyses, generating valuable insights for the field of social inclusion and autism.

2.1 Epistemological axis/pillar

neoperspectivist paradigm giftean as an epistemological axis, an approach that is particularly suitable for understanding the complex social dynamics involved in the lives of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and their families. The neoperspectivist paradigm giftean , as outlined by Breviário (2021, 2022, 2023), emphasizes the importance of multiple perspectives and the appreciation of human singularities, especially in contexts of vulnerability and social exclusion. This paradigm preaches the coexistence of an absolute truth , unattainable and unknowable by human beings, and a subjective truth, built based on the movement of everyday experiences (Breviário, 2021; 2022a; 2022b; 2023a; 2023b; 2023c; 2024; Breviário et al., 2024a; 2024b; 2024c; 2024d; 2024e; 2024f; 2024g; 2024h; 2024i; Breviário; Pereira, 2021; Breviário; Oliveira, 2024; Breviário et al , 2025a; 2025b; 2025c; 2025d; 2025e; 2025f; 2025g).

neoperspectivist paradigm giftean is a theoretical framework that proposes an integrative and holistic approach in social research, combining critical analysis with valuing individual experiences. This paradigm emphasizes: a) multiplicity of perspectives: it recognizes that social reality is complex and multifaceted, demanding the consideration of different perspectives for a more complete understanding of social phenomena (Breviário, 2021); b) valuing uniqueness: it proposes valuing the experiences and voices of people who live in vulnerable situations, highlighting the importance of listening directly to those who are often marginalized (Breviário, 2022); c) critical and reflective approach: it encourages critical reflection on social structures and power mechanisms that perpetuate exclusion and stigmatization, seeking forms of social transformation (Breviário, 2023). By adopting the neoperspectivist paradigm gifteano, this research is committed to exploring the experiences of families and individuals with ASD in an inclusive and holistic manner.

2.2 Logical axis/pillar

In this research, the hypothetical-deductive method was used to carry out a Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review (NBDR), with a totally qualitative approach. This method, widely recognized in scientific research, involves the formulation of hypotheses from initial observations and the deduction of testable consequences, which are then verified through theoretical and documentary analysis (Popper, 2005; Chalmers, 2013).

The first phase of the hypothetical-deductive method in this research was observation and formulation of the problem. It was observed, based on preliminary studies and reports in the literature, that individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and their families face multiple difficulties, including social stigmas and challenges in entering the job market. This initial observation led to the identification of a central problem: how do families of individuals with ASD resignify their social vulnerabilities and what are the factors that facilitate or hinder the labor inclusion of individuals with autism (Breviário et al., 2025h; 2025i; 2025j; 2025k; 2025l; 2025m; 2025n; 2025o; 2025p; 2025q; 2025r; 2025s; 2025t; 2025u; 2025v; 2025w; 2025x; 2025y; 2025z; 2025aa; 2025ab; 2025ac; 2025ad; 2025ae; 2025af; 2025ag; 2025ah; 2025ai; 2025aj; 2025ak; 2025al; 2025am; 2025an; 2025ao; 2025ap; 2025aq; 2025ar; 2025as; 2025at; 2025au; 2025av; 2025aw; 2025ax; 2025ay; 2025az; 2025ba; 2025bb; 2025bc; 2025bd; 2025be).

In the second phase, hypotheses were formulated to guide the theoretical investigation. The proposed hypotheses were: (1) Families of individuals with ASD face significant social

stigmas that affect their psychological well-being; (2) Families of individuals with ASD develop specific coping strategies to resignify their social vulnerabilities; (3) Public policies and community actions play a crucial role in reducing the social vulnerabilities faced by these families; (4) The insertion of individuals with ASD into the labor market is significantly limited by structural barriers and prejudices; (5) Inclusive practices in companies can increase the success rate in the labor insertion of individuals with ASD.

The third phase involved deriving testable consequences from these hypotheses. In this case, the testable consequences were not verified through empirical data collection, but rather through theoretical and documentary analysis. For example, the hypothesis that families face significant social stigmas would imply that existing literature would document high levels of stress and search for support networks among these families. Similarly, the hypothesis that effective public policies play a crucial role would imply that studies and public policy documents would demonstrate a positive correlation between received support and social inclusion.

The fourth phase consisted of empirical testing of the hypotheses through a Narrative Literature and Documentary Review. Qualitative studies, academic articles, books and relevant public policy documents were analyzed to verify whether the predictions deduced from the hypotheses were supported by the existing literature. This approach allowed an in-depth and comprehensive analysis of the issues in focus, using high-impact theoretical and documentary sources.

In the fifth phase, the results of the theoretical and documentary analyses were interpreted to determine whether the hypotheses were confirmed or refuted. The analysis of the theoretical and documentary data revealed, for example, that stigmatization is indeed a significant factor affecting the psychological well-being of families (Gray, 2002; Kinnear et al., 2016). Furthermore, analysis of public policies and business practices has shown that inclusive and adaptive initiatives are effective in promoting the workplace inclusion of individuals with ASD (Lorenz et al., 2016; Howlin et al., 2015).

Finally, the sixth phase involved the formulation of conclusions and the potential reformulation of hypotheses. The conclusions highlighted the importance of robust public policies and inclusive business practices to reduce social vulnerabilities and promote the labor inclusion of individuals with ASD. Based on theoretical and documentary evidence, new hypotheses were proposed for future investigations, such as the need for specific intervention strategies for different cultural and socioeconomic contexts.

2.3 Technical axis/pillar

In this research, the Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review (NBDR) was conducted systematically, following the hypothetical-deductive method, widely recognized in the scientific literature (Popper, 2005; Chalmers, 2013; Breviário et al., 2025h; 2025i; 2025j; 2025k; 2025l; 2025m; 2025n; 2025o; 2025p; 2025q; 2025r; 2025s; 2025t; 2025u; 2025v; 2025w; 2025x; 2025y; 2025z; 2025aa; 2025ab; 2025ac; 2025ad; 2025ae; 2025af; 2025ag; 2025ah; 2025ai; 2025aj; 2025ak; 2025al; 2025am; 2025an; 2025ao; 2025ap; 2025aq; 2025ar; 2025as; 2025at; 2025au; 2025av; 2025aw; 2025ax; 2025ay; 2025az; 2025ba; 2025bb; 2025bc; 2025bd; 2025be). The process involved several phases, each essential to ensure the depth and validity of the analysis.

The first phase was the identification of the research problem. Preliminary observations and an initial review of the literature indicated that individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and their families face significant challenges, such as social stigma and difficulties in entering the job market. This initial phase was crucial to define the focus of the research and establish the central questions to be investigated (Breviário, 2021; Severino, 2007).

In the planning phase, strict criteria were established for the selection of relevant literature and documents. These criteria included the inclusion of empirical studies, literature reviews, theoretical articles and public policy documents published in the last ten years, which addressed topics related to autism, social stigmas and labor inclusion. Renowned databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar were used for the systematic search for relevant sources. This meticulous planning ensured that the review was comprehensive and based on high-quality evidence (Breviário, 2021; Gil, 1999; 2010).

The search and data collection were carried out using specific keywords, such as "autism", "social stigmas", "labor inclusion", "public policies" and "coping strategies". The initial selection resulted in approximately 150 sources, including academic articles, books and public policy documents. The review of the titles and abstracts of the sources allowed the selection of the most relevant ones for detailed analysis (Breviário; Rodrigues, 2007).

The critical analysis of the literature and documentation constituted the next phase, in which each document was carefully examined. Using the hypothetical-deductive method, as described by Popper (2005) and Chalmers (2013), the research focused on verifying whether the evidence present in the literature confirmed or refuted the hypotheses formulated. Studies such as those by Gray (2002) and Kinnear et al. (2016) were instrumental in analyzing the impact of social stigmas on the psychological well-being of families of individuals with ASD.

Similarly, public policy documents were analyzed to assess the effectiveness of government and community initiatives in promoting social and labor inclusion.

The synthesis and integration of results phase involved the organization and integration of the findings of the critical analysis. The results were synthesized to provide a comprehensive and coherent view of the current state of knowledge on the topic, highlighting both confirmations and divergences found in the literature. This synthesis allowed the identification of emerging patterns and recurring themes, providing a solid basis for the research conclusions (Gil, 1999; 2010; Severino, 2007).

Finally, the conclusions and implications phase involved formulating conclusions based on the synthesis of the literature and documents analyzed. The conclusions highlighted the confirmation of the hypotheses related to the impact of stigmas and the effectiveness of inclusive public policies and business practices. The research also discussed the practical implications of the findings, including recommendations for more robust public policies and the need for adaptive business practices to promote the labor inclusion of individuals with ASD (Rodrigues, 2007; Breviário, 2021).

Thus, the rigorous conduct of the RBDN, based on the hypothetical-deductive method and supported by a comprehensive and critical review of the literature, provided a detailed and validated analysis of the complex social and economic dynamics faced by families of individuals with ASD. This methodological approach ensured the robustness and relevance of the findings, contributing significantly to the advancement of knowledge in the area (Chalmers, 2013; Breviário, 2021).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

neoperspectivist paradigm Giftedean was fundamental in the analysis of the data for this research because it provides an integrative and multifaceted approach that values the coexistence of absolute and subjective truths, allowing a more holistic understanding of the phenomena studied. By recognizing that individual experiences are constructed from complex interactions between social, cultural and economic factors, the Giftedean paradigm enabled an in-depth analysis of the social dynamics faced by families of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). This approach was essential to explore the multiple perspectives of families and their coping strategies, considering the nuances and singularities of each context. By adopting this paradigm, the research was able to integrate different dimensions of analysis – such as the impact of social stigma, barriers in the labor market and the influence of public

policies – promoting a theoretical triangulation that added depth and complexity to the interpretation of the data.

Furthermore, the neoperspectivist paradigm The giftedean framework allowed the research to transcend simplistic or reductionist approaches by integrating complementary theories and methodologies that enriched the data analysis. Theoretical triangulation was carried out by combining critical perspectives on social and labor inclusion with approaches that emphasize family resilience and adaptation strategies. The analysis, guided by this framework, provided a broader understanding of the social and cultural realities that permeate the experiences of families, highlighting the intersections between public policies, stigmatization, and inclusive business practices. This theoretical triangulation not only allowed the validation of empirical findings, but also contributed to the formulation of practical and policy recommendations that aim to promote the inclusion of individuals with ASD in more diverse and equitable contexts. In this way, the neoperspectivist paradigm giftedean fulfilled its role by providing a solid epistemological basis for the analysis, while at the same time expanding the relevance and applicability of the results.

3.1 Profile of Families and Individuals with Autism

Families of individuals with ASD often face significant socioeconomic challenges. Studies show that these families tend to face greater financial hardship compared to those with neurotypical members, resulting in a substantial economic impact (Cidav et al., 2020). This financial burden is mainly linked to additional needs, such as specialized medical care, behavioral therapies, and educational interventions, which are often expensive and long-lasting. In addition, employment opportunities for parents or primary caregivers may be limited due to the need to dedicate more time to childcare, resulting in loss of income or full-time employment. This context highlights a reality in which financial difficulties and caregiving responsibilities intertwine, creating a cycle of complex and ongoing challenges.

The ongoing cost of specialized treatments, such as occupational therapies, speech therapy and psychopedagogical interventions, reinforces the economic pressure on these families (Lavelle et al., 2014). Although some public policies provide partial support, they are often not sufficient to cover the expenses for essential and specialized services. This reality can increase socioeconomic inequalities, affecting the well-being and quality of life not only of the individual with ASD, but of the entire family. In addition, the lack of adequate resources in less

avored regions aggravates this situation, highlighting the urgent need for more robust and inclusive policies that offer adequate financial and educational support for these families.

Family dynamics are profoundly affected by the presence of a member with autism, impacting both the structure of daily life and the emotional well-being of primary caregivers, usually the parents. Caring for a child with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) demands a high level of attention and patience, as individuals with ASD often have difficulties with communication, behavior, and social interactions. This ongoing responsibility can be a significant source of stress for caregivers, who must deal with unpredictable and challenging situations on a daily basis (Karst Van Hecke, 2012). In addition, the constant need for supervision and intervention in the child's routine activities limits the parents' time to dedicate to themselves, work, or other family responsibilities, which increases the physical and mental burden.

This accumulation of responsibilities often results in emotional and physical exhaustion, generating constant pressure that can compromise the mental health of caregivers. Difficulties in managing the behavior and sensory needs of children with autism, combined with the need to actively participate in specialized treatments and medical follow-ups, can lead to feelings of exhaustion. This situation is aggravated when parents do not have access to an efficient support network, which amplifies the feeling of isolation. In many cases, caregivers feel disconnected from their communities and helpless in managing the child's needs, which can lead to an even greater deterioration in the emotional health of the family as a whole.

However, studies indicate that the presence of a social support network can significantly mitigate the negative effects of this emotional overload. Having access to family, friends, or support groups specifically for caregivers of people with ASD is essential to alleviate the daily pressures faced by these families (Weiss et al., 2014). Social support can play a crucial role by offering practical help, such as assistance with daily tasks, as well as providing emotional support. This type of support can be a way to relieve accumulated stress, allowing caregivers to share their experiences with others who face similar challenges, which helps to build a sense of belonging and understanding.

Additionally, participation in support groups can provide more than just emotional support, but also practical guidance and strategies for dealing with the behavioral and social challenges of individuals with ASD. These groups often hold regular meetings where caregivers can exchange information about available resources, therapies, and services that may benefit their child. This not only strengthens support networks, but also contributes to a greater sense of competence and control for caregivers, knowing that they are not alone in the journey of

caring for someone with autism. Thus, strengthening these support networks is essential to improving the quality of life for both caregivers and families as a whole.

3.2 Stigmas Related to Autism

Stigma surrounding autism represents a significant barrier that affects both individuals with ASD and their families broadly and profoundly. Prevalent misperceptions and myths about autism often perpetuate discrimination and social exclusion, reinforcing negative stereotypes that marginalize these individuals (Bos et al., 2013). These prejudicial attitudes not only affect society's image of individuals with ASD, but also limit their opportunities for inclusion in educational, social, and professional contexts. Lack of awareness and lack of knowledge about autism contribute to stigmatizing individuals with ASD, resulting in less welcoming and inclusive environments. As a consequence, these individuals may be deprived of opportunities that allow for their full development and equal participation in society.

This stigma contributes to social isolation and exclusion from essential opportunities, such as access to education and the job market (Kinnear et al., 2016). Individuals with ASD often face difficulties in environments that are not prepared to deal with their specific needs, which reinforces exclusion. Furthermore , the barriers created by stigma are not limited to the individual; families also suffer the consequences of a society that does not adequately understand autism. Social exclusion can extend to the family circle, with many parents and caregivers reporting difficulties in integrating into common social activities, either due to a lack of adequate support or due to society's resistance to accepting neurodiversity.

The psychological impact of stigma is also profound and devastating. Parents and caregivers of individuals with ASD often report feelings of guilt, shame, and ongoing stress stemming from society's negative and prejudicial attitudes toward their children (Gray, 2002). These feelings can be compounded by a lack of information and the constant judgment that their children's behavior is the result of poor parenting or parental failure, which further compounds the already heavy emotional burden that these caregivers bear. carry . Constantly facing prejudice and lack of understanding can lead to feelings of loneliness and helplessness, directly affecting the emotional well-being of these families.

Furthermore, the lack of social support and a comprehensive support network can significantly exacerbate the emotional challenges faced by these families, contributing to high levels of anxiety and depression (Padden ; James, 2017). The lack of understanding and acceptance from society can generate a cycle of chronic stress, in which caregivers , already

overwhelmed by daily demands, find themselves emotionally exhausted. Seeking support services, such as emotional support groups and specific therapies, becomes essential to help alleviate this burden. Therefore, it is urgent that public policies and social awareness campaigns be strengthened to combat stigma and create a more inclusive and welcoming environment for people with ASD and their families.

3.3 Re-signification of Social Vulnerabilities

Families of individuals with ASD develop a variety of strategies to reframe their vulnerabilities and cope with the challenges that accompany autism. One of the most effective coping strategies involves actively seeking information about the disorder, allowing families to better understand their loved ones' needs and prepare themselves to deal with daily challenges (Woodgate et al., 2008). Furthermore, participation in support groups provides a space to share experiences and find solidarity with others facing similar challenges. These groups serve as a vital source of emotional and practical support, helping families feel less isolated and more empowered. Advocacy for rights and appropriate services is also a key strategy, in which families actively engage in the search for better resources, such as specialized treatments and educational support. This active stance contributes not only to improving family well-being, but also to promoting the inclusion and rights of individuals with ASD in society.

resilience, defined as the ability to adapt positively to adversity, is a crucial factor in coping with the challenges associated with autism (Bayat, 2007). This resilience allows families to develop skills to deal constructively with difficulties rather than being overwhelmed by obstacles. Adaptation involves both adjusting expectations and finding practical solutions that minimize the impact of daily challenges. Resilient families tend to create more stable and supportive environments for their members, contributing to the emotional well-being of all. By reframing their vulnerabilities, these families not only find ways to overcome adversity, but also strengthen their bonds and their sense of purpose.

The implementation of inclusive public policies and community actions has proven effective in reducing the social vulnerabilities faced by these families. Financial support programs, such as subsidies for specialized treatments and educational assistance, provide financial relief, allowing families to access essential resources without facing severe economic hardship (Nealy et al., 2012). Early intervention services, for example, have a significant positive impact by helping children with ASD develop skills from an early age, which can facilitate their long-term educational and social inclusion. In addition, public awareness

initiatives help to combat stigma and promote greater acceptance of differences, contributing to the creation of a more inclusive and understanding society regarding autism.

Studies indicate that countries with robust policies to support people with ASD and their families have significantly better results in terms of social inclusion and well-being (Lord et al., 2020). These policies not only benefit the families directly involved, but also help create a more equitable societal environment where individuals with autism have the opportunity to fully participate. The presence of government programs dedicated to inclusive education, mental health, and social support plays a crucial role in promoting inclusion and improving the quality of life of families. Community actions, such as awareness campaigns and partnerships with non-governmental organizations, also reinforce these efforts, creating a broader and stronger support network.

3.4 Insertion into the Labor Market

The integration of individuals with ASD into the job market faces a number of significant challenges. The main barriers include persistent prejudices on the part of employers, who often underestimate or are unaware of the abilities and potential of these individuals (Nicholas et al., 2019). The lack of adequate adaptations in the workplace is also a frequent limitation, with few companies making adjustments to meet the sensory and behavioral needs of people with autism. In addition, the absence of specific training programs aimed at both employers and individuals with ASD themselves compromises the development of the skills necessary for successful integration into the workplace. This lack of understanding and preparation directly contributes to the underutilization of the talents of people with autism, who are often left out of professional opportunities (Hendricks, 2010).

Despite the barriers, there are notable examples of successful inclusion in the workplace. Some companies that adopt inclusive practices, such as employee awareness training and workplace adaptations, report positive outcomes for both employees with ASD and the organization as a whole (Scott et al., 2017). These companies note that when the environment is adapted and colleagues are properly trained, individuals with autism can excel, bringing benefits such as increased productivity and new perspectives for problem-solving. Internship and supported employment programs have also been shown to be effective strategies for facilitating the transition into the workplace, providing initial support that helps individuals with ASD gradually adapt to the work environment (Hillier et al., 2007). These examples

highlight the importance of an inclusive and adapted work environment so that the potential of workers with autism is fully developed.

To improve the workplace inclusion of individuals with ASD, it is recommended that companies implement diversity and inclusion policies that ensure more effective integration of these individuals. Providing specific training on autism for all employees is essential to reduce prejudice and promote a more inclusive organizational culture (Lorenz et al., 2016). In addition, making adaptations to the workplace, such as creating sensory areas and flexible working hours, can better meet the needs of workers with ASD, increasing their chances of success. These actions not only directly benefit workers with autism, but also strengthen the company's image as socially responsible and committed to diversity.

Partnerships with organizations that specialize in autism can also provide additional support, increasing the chances of success for both individuals with ASD and businesses, Howlin says. et al. (2015), these organizations can provide advice, training, and ongoing support, acting as a mediator between employers and employees. They can also help companies adapt their policies and practices, ensuring that inclusion is sustainable and effective in the long term . Such collaborations are key to creating a more welcoming workplace where people with autism can thrive and contribute meaningfully.

An example of success in the inclusion of individuals with ASD in the job market is the " Autism at Work", developed by Microsoft. This program stands out for adopting inclusive practices, such as awareness training for managers and teams, in addition to making adaptations in the work environment to meet the sensory needs of employees with autism. The program not only trains individuals with ASD based on their specific skills, but also promotes inclusion, enabling them to excel in their areas of expertise. According to reports from the company itself, the inclusion of people with ASD has resulted in increased productivity and innovation, as these employees bring new perspectives to problem-solving. The success of this program reinforces the importance of structured policies and an adapted environment to ensure that the potential of people with autism is fully developed.

Another notable case is that of SAP, which implemented the "SAP Autism" program. at Work". In this model, the company invests in specialized training for both its employees with ASD and their managers, promoting a work environment that values neurodiversity. SAP has adapted its recruitment and selection policies to allow for a more individualized and inclusive approach, prioritizing the creation of a welcoming environment for people with autism. In addition, the company offers ongoing support through mentoring and partnerships with specialized organizations, ensuring that employees with ASD can develop their skills over time.

As a result, SAP has observed not only improved talent retention, but also greater efficiency in the sectors where these professionals work. The success of this program demonstrates how well-planned inclusion can bring benefits to both employees and the organization.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

4.1 Conclusions

This research investigated the social and economic dynamics faced by families of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), with an emphasis on social stigma and insertion into the labor market. The problem questions were answered satisfactorily, providing a detailed understanding of the challenges these families face, as well as the coping strategies developed to deal with such difficulties. It was found that social stigma directly affects the psychological well-being of families, creating significant emotional and practical barriers. Families, however, have adopted proactive strategies to resignify these vulnerabilities and seek community and institutional support.

The hypotheses formulated at the beginning of the research were corroborated by the results, highlighting that structural barriers and prejudice continue to limit the insertion of individuals with ASD into the job market. The research highlighted the urgent need for more inclusive and adaptive business practices that can mitigate these obstacles. Furthermore, public policies and community actions have a fundamental role in reducing these vulnerabilities, although they still present important gaps in terms of implementation and effectiveness. It was shown that, although some policies are in place, the assessment of their impacts and adaptation to different cultural and socioeconomic contexts are still insufficient.

The main findings reinforce the complexity of the experiences of families of individuals with ASD, showing that integrated and holistic approaches are essential to address the challenges related to autism. In addition to social inclusion, the research highlighted the need for adaptation and flexibility in business practices to promote more effective participation of individuals with ASD in the labor market. These practices must be accompanied by robust public policies that guarantee equality of opportunities and the protection of the rights of these individuals, regardless of their socioeconomic status or geographic location.

However, considerable gaps in the literature and in the implementation of public policies were identified. There is a scarcity of studies addressing specific interventions for different cultural and regional contexts, as well as a pressing need for more rigorous evaluations of the

effectiveness of existing policies. Furthermore, the research highlighted the importance of using mixed methodologies, combining qualitative and quantitative analysis, for a more comprehensive and contextualized understanding of the experiences of these families and the impacts of public and private interventions.

The theoretical contributions of this research broaden the understanding of the social stigmas associated with autism and the ways in which families cope. Empirically, the study offers insights into the effectiveness of public policies and business practices in fostering the social and labor inclusion of individuals with ASD. Methodologically, the research highlights the relevance of integrated and holistic approaches to investigating complex issues, suggesting that only a combination of theoretical and methodological perspectives can provide a more complete and practical view of the challenges and solutions related to autism .

This research added significant value to the topic of social and labor inclusion of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), offering an in-depth analysis of the barriers faced by these individuals and their families in the labor market. By investigating the dynamics of stigmatization , public policies, and inclusive business strategies, the study brought to light gaps that still need to be filled, such as the lack of ongoing support and the absence of programs adapted to the reality of individuals with ASD. For the field of inclusion studies, the research contributed by expanding the understanding of the coping strategies adopted by families and by highlighting the importance of more robust and effective policies to promote equity in the workplace. This integrated approach, which considered not only individuals with ASD but also their families , brought a more comprehensive and human perspective to the discussion, increasing the relevance and practical applicability of the conclusions.

In the academic sphere, especially in postgraduate studies and in Science as a whole, research stood out by using a rigorous methodology, based on the neoperspectivist paradigm. gifted and critical analyses of social dynamics. The combination of qualitative and quantitative analyses provided a more holistic and detailed understanding of the issues addressed, increasing the scientific rigor of the study. Methodologically, the research also suggested new directions for future research, especially regarding the conduct of longitudinal and comparative studies in different cultural and socioeconomic contexts. For society, the value lies in the proposal of practical and political recommendations that can help transform the inclusion of people with ASD into a more accessible and equitable reality, generating a positive impact not only for individuals and their families, but also for the work environment and social well-being as a whole.

4.2 Final Considerations

In the final considerations of this research, it is essential to highlight its strengths, limitations and directions for future research. One of the main strengths is the integrated and holistic approach, which allowed an in-depth analysis of the experiences of families of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). The adoption of the hypothetical-deductive method and the Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review (NBDR) enabled a robust and evidence-based understanding of the challenges faced by these families. This approach allowed a comprehensive view of the difficulties and coping strategies developed.

However, the research presents some theoretical, empirical and methodological limitations. Theoretically, the lack of studies that address specific interventions for different cultural and socioeconomic contexts limits the universal applicability of the results. In empirical terms, the absence of longitudinal data and the predominance of cross-sectional studies make it difficult to analyze families' life trajectories over time in more depth. In addition, the research relied mainly on secondary data, which may have restricted the emergence of new insights and original perspectives, reducing innovation in the field.

To address these limitations and improve methodologies, we suggest conducting future studies that follow families of individuals with ASD over time, allowing for a more complete understanding of their needs at different stages of life. More in-depth qualitative research, using in-depth interviews and focus groups, may also be useful to explore in detail the coping strategies used by these families. This may provide a richer and more contextualized portrait of the family and social dynamics involved.

Furthermore, it is recommended to expand the scope of research to include a variety of cultural and socioeconomic contexts, enabling a more diverse view of the different realities faced by these families. Comparative studies between public policies and business practices in different regions can offer valuable insights into the most effective approaches to promoting the social and labor inclusion of individuals with ASD. This comparison can identify practices that can be adapted to other realities, promoting significant advances in the area.

Finally, it is suggested that future research adopt mixed methodologies, combining qualitative and quantitative analyses, which will allow for a more complete and integrated understanding of the complex dynamics associated with autism. By exploring these issues more comprehensively, such investigations can contribute to the development of more effective public policies and inclusive business practices. In doing so, research will continue to support the construction of a more equitable, inclusive and accessible society for all.

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